

Tang Junyi 唐君毅

also known as “Tang Chun-i”

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Entry tags: Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Huayan school (huayan zong 華嚴宗), Religious Group, Text, Buddhist Traditions, Contemporary Neo-Confucianism, Modern Classics in Chinese Philosophy, Self-Cultivation, Chinese Religion, Confucianism

Tang Junyi (唐君毅, 1909 – 1978) was one of the most influential thinkers in modern Chinese society, especially in Hong Kong and Taiwan. Widely considered a member of ‘Contemporary Neo-Confucianism’, Tang employed Buddhist ideas, Huayan thought in particular, to develop his philosophical system, which tried to harmonize different valuable thoughts so that they could co-exist without conflict. Within this harmonization, one could, on the one hand, choose his or her faith, while on the other hand, would not reject others’. Tang clearly stated that he believed in Confucianism, an intellectual tradition which pays attention to the existence of consciousness or benevolence, as he considered the thought most relevant to his own moral experience. There were some examples that Tang stressed throughout his writings: while once seeing the land split due to drought in his childhood, he worried that the earth would soon end; while watching a movie about Sun Yat-sen (孫逸仙, 1866 – 1925), the founder of the Republic of China, he wondered, compared with the whole universe, how little a human being was but how great a human being could achieve; while separating from his parents, he genuinely felt sadness. As Tang said, all of his philosophical thought derived from such moral experience and, therefore, his thought could be understood as his explanation to the existence of consciousness, how it worked and what would be achieved if it was fully utilized. Tang’s complete works were initially published in Taiwan in 1991, and a revised edition was released in mainland China in 2016. Despite Tang’s obscure writing style, many of his works are considered modern classics in the field of Chinese philosophy. The Experience of Life 人生之體驗, for example, suggests different moral experiences a human may face in his or her life, in which Tang reflected the moral ability a human could have and the function of such ability. The Formation of Moral Self 道德自我之建立, tries to explain the existence of the moral ability from a philosophical perspective, claiming that moral ability is not only an experience felt by individual persons but a universal faculty that owned by all people. The Reconstruction of Humanistic Spirit 人文精神之重建 mentions Tang’s ultimate ideal, which is to make the world full of humanistic values by means of fully utilizing the moral abilities of all persons. The Existence of Life and Horizons of Mind 生命存在與心靈境界, his last and probably the most important work, explains that the real humanistic value is exactly not to reject any valuable thoughts and how moral ability helps harmonize different values so that a humanistic world could be achieved. As Tang always emphasized the importance of self-transformation and his works tend to encourage and inspire others to transform, some scholars considered that the nature of Tang’s thought is like a kind of religion, though his faith is not in an external god, but in the internal goodness of humanity.

Date Range: 1930 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Beijing, Shanghai, Hong Kong, and Taiwan

Region tags: Asia, Taiwan, East Asia, China, Hong Kong Special Administration Region

Areas of importance for Contemporary Neo-Confucianism

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 吳汝鈞等，《唐君毅哲學的對話詮釋》(台北：台灣學生書局，2019年)。
- Source 2: 李杜，《唐君毅先生的哲學》(台北：台灣學生書局，1989年)。
- Source 3: 勞思光，《思光人物論集》(香港：香港中文大學出版社，2001年)。
- Source 1: King Pong Chiu, Thomé H. Fang, Tang Junyi and Huayan Thought: A Confucian Appropriation of Buddhist Ideas in Response to Scientism in Twentieth-Century China (Leiden: Brill, 2016).
- Source 2: Thomas Fröhlich, Tang Junyi: Confucian Philosophy and the Challenge of Modernity (Leiden: Brill, 2017).
- Source 3: Jana S. Rošker, The Rebirth of the Moral Self: The Second Generation of Modern Confucians and their Modernization Discourses (Hong Kong: The Chinese University Press, 2016).
- Source 1: 趙敬邦，《即凡見聖：唐君毅人學論》(台北：台大出版中心，2023年)。
- Source 2: 趙敬邦，《唐君毅與香港》(新竹：聯經，2023年)。
- Source 3: 黃冠閔，《感通與迴盪：唐君毅哲學論探》(台北：聯經，2018年)。

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: n/a

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: n/a

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– without Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Specify type of paper

– Specify: n/a

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: n/a

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: n/a

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: Ideally, the estimated number of audiences of the text is approximately those attentive to the future of Confucianism and Chinese culture, though the actual number of audiences was rather limited during the time of Tang and after his death. As Tang said around a year before his death, he was disappointed that his works did not gain enough attention and were not understood by those who read them. Therefore, he did feel lonely in his last few years.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: As Tang is broadly considered a key member of the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', the issue about recruiting new members needs to consider the characteristics of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'. On the one hand, anyone who shares the ideal of the figures of the 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' could consider him or herself a member of the group. On the other hand, the membership seems to only belong to those who have studied under the figures of the 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism'. Therefore, the so-called membership is very open while at the same time rather exclusive. And there is no strict process to recruit new members.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Tang Junyi, together with Ch'ien Mu (錢穆, 1895 - 1990) and Zhang Pijie (張丕介, 1905 - 1970), found the New Asia College in Hong Kong in 1949. As Tang argued, the aim of the College was to promote a kind of humanism, which he considered a response to the materialism and totalitarianism spreading in Asia and even the world in that time. Tang also claimed that what they needed was another Renaissance and, therefore, both the New Asia College and the works of Tang were actually a part of a cultural reformist movement. For details, see 趙敬邦, 《唐君毅與香港》(新竹: 聯經, 2023年).

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: To a large extent, Tang's works are considered a part of the tradition of Confucianism.

Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: It depends on the definition of 'religion'. To a large extent, Tang's works are regarded as philosophy. At least, it is observed that they are taught in philosophy departments but not departments of religion studies in Chinese universities. However, Tang stressed that his thought is not to provide philosophical knowledge but to help people transform themselves. In this sense, individual thinker like Lao Sze-kwang (勞思光, 1927 - 2012) considered that the nature of Tang's thought is like certain kind of religion, which emphasizes self-transformation. In this regard, there are religious implications in Tang's works.

Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: As the initial aim of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' is to help people transform themselves, the works of Tang could be considered a kind of behavioral literature, which is to encourage and inspire others to improve.

Other

–Other [specify]: n/a

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Index

– Vocabulary

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: Although many scholars think that Tang's works, together with those written by Mou Zongsan (牟宗三, 1909 - 1995), follow the scholarship of Xiong Shili (熊十力, 1885 -1968), one of the most

important Confucian thinkers in the last century and probably the master of the group of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', Tang stressed that he was not affected by Xiong. Instead, his thought was influenced by many thinkers. In this sense, no single lineage is seen in the text. For details, see 趙敬邦, 《即凡見聖：唐君毅人學論》(台北：台大出版中心，2023年).

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: One of main arguments in Tang's works is that there is a spirit-body distinction for humans. To Tang, 'spirit' does exist beyond a body. However, this 'spirit' is not equal to a soul but some spiritual activities that a person shows to others, such as wishes, moral abilities and even emotion. Such activities can be 'felt' by others and, as a result, humans can communicate with each other through the contact of 'spirit' without obstruction.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: As Tang argues, there is no 'limits' for 'spirit' and humans could enhance their spiritual activities whenever they want. However, there is always limits for other parts of the body. One needs to follow the limitations no matter whether he or she likes them or not.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

Notes: There are both positive and negative associations with aggregates. However, Tang mainly pays his attention to the positive ones as it is considered that once the positive associations functions, the negative ones would not work.

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: n/a

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

Notes: In *Minds, Material and Life* 心物與人生, one of Tang's early works, Tang tries to discuss such a distinction and it is based on this understanding that he develops his philosophical thought, which aims to help others to enhance their 'spirits'. For those following Tang's thought, the debate is always remembered.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that though 'spirit' is considered more fundamental, Tang also stresses the importance of body as it is through the latter that the former could better manifest.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: As 'spirit' manifests through body, Tang does not consider there is a clear dualism between mind and body. The relationship between mind and body, to a large extent, is cooperative rather than contradictory.

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: Tang's position is mostly within the historical mainstream of Confucianism.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: As Tang explicitly stated, he believed in the existence of 'soul'. However, the soul as he understood is the spirit activities one manifests. These activities could end one day but they could also be 'felt' and even followed by others. In this sense, one could live in others' lives even though the former has been dead.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– Yes

Notes: In general, the stronger one's spirit activities are, the longer the afterlife one enjoys.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: As 'spirit' means spiritual activities, the 'spirits' of previous people are still existing if the spiritual activities of such people were great enough. To Tang, the 'spirits' of Confucius, Buddha and Jesus, for example, are still here as many people in present days are still following their thoughts and practices.

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams
 - No
 - ↳ In trance possession
 - No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

–Specify: According to Tang, the 'spirit' of a person could be 'felt' by others. As long as a person eager to enhance his or her 'spirit', others would communicate with him or her automatically.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: As Tang argued in his *The Experience of Life 人生之體驗*, 'In the World of Truth, all truths are mutually penetrative, with an absolute Truth as its centre. This absolute Truth is your passion for truths itself.' In this sense, non-human supernatural beings, if there is any, are ultimately developed by humans.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: n/a

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism' believes that the fate of the world depends on the quality of human beings. In order to make the world into a better place, one needs to improve the quality of him or herself first, and try to help others to improve themselves. The ultimate aim of such improvement is to improve the world so that humans can live a better life. In this sense, both Messianism or Eschatology depend on the choice of humans, but not a 'supernatural being' beyond them. As a key figure of 'Contemporary Neo-Confucianism', Tang followed this position. To be more precise, he helped construct such a point of view.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

Notes: Since Tang wrote most of his works during the time of the Second World War and Cold War, it is observed that he sometimes considered that the eschaton would be in this lifetime. It could be too late if humans did nothing to improve the situation.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future
– Yes

↳ At unspecified time in distant future
– No

↳ At some other time [specify]
– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
– No

↳ Divine judgment event
– No

↳ Restoration of the world
– Yes

Notes: As the name of his work *The Reconstruction of Humanistic Spirit* 人文精神之重建 shows, Tang argued that humans should restore a kind of humanism as soon as possible in order to save the world.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
– No

↳ Establishment of new political system
– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system
– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?
– Specify: n/a

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– No

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– Yes

Notes: As stated previously, the fate of humans is decided by humans themselves. Theoretically, therefore, all humans could be saved if the quality of humans are to be improved.

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

–Specify: n/a

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: The act of humans depends on situations, and there is no strict universal social norm that one needs to follow. However, all acts need to meet one's conscience or the value of humaneness (or Ren 仁 in Confucian term). In this sense, humaneness or Ren is the general social norm one needs to follow, though the interpretation of Ren is always open but not rigid, depending on the situation individual faces.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: To Tang, moral values are manifested in one's daily living. Therefore, there is no clear conventional vs. moral distinction in the thought.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: In principle, Tang supported the acts which are reflected by humans as righteous. Although how one manifests such righteousness varies among situations.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle)
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity/charity
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - Yes

- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– No

↳ Other important virtues
– Yes

Notes: In principle, Tang supported the acts which are reflected by humans as righteous. Although how one manifests such righteousness varies among situations.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: As Tang admitted, he wrote his works in an obscure way as he held the view that truth would never be understood easily and one needs to spend time on obtaining it. In this sense, Tang may consider that reading his works is a sacrifice of time and it is a must for reaching the truth.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: A group of scholars who believes in Confucianism.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: n/a

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: n/a

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No